

PLANNING TRAINING AND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF HANDBALL PLAYERS' COMPETITION ACTIVITIES.

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Rezyume:

Maqalada gandbolshilardıń jarıs iskerliginde TTH (texnikalıq hám taktikalıq háreketler) di dizimnen ótkeriw hám ulıwma komanda háreketleriniń natiyjeliligin anıqlaw hámde keyingi shınıǵıwlardı jobalastırıw hám tártipke salıw haqqında usınıslar berilgen.

Резюме:

В статье даются рекомендации по систематическому осуществлению технико-тактических действий в соревновательной деятельности гандболистов и определению эффективности общекомандных действий, а также планированию и организации последующей тренировки.

Resume:

The article provides recommendations for the systematic implementation of technical and tactical actions in the competitive activities of handball players and determining the effectiveness of team actions, as well as planning and organizing subsequent training.

Tayanısh sózler: texnika,taktika,shınıǵıw,hújim,qorǵanıw,jarıs.individual, soqqı,dárwazaban.

Texnik,taktik,mashg'ulot,xujim,ximoya,musobaqa,individual,zarba.darvozabon

Ключевые слова: Технический, тактический, тренировочный, атакующий, оборонительный, соревновательный, индивидуальный, ударный, вратарь.

Key words: Technical, tactical, training, attacking, defensive, competitive, individual, striking, goalkeeper

INTRODUCTION

The formation of a healthy lifestyle in our society, the creation of conditions in accordance with the requirements of the time for the physical education of the people, especially the younger generation, and the uninterrupted practice of mass sports, confidence in self-resistance, strength and capabilities in young people with sports competitions, strengthening courage and patriotism, maturing feelings of loyalty to the motherland, at the same time, large-scale work aimed at the systematic organization of the selection of talented athletes among young people, as well as the further development of physical education and mass sports is being carried out.

The high performance of the representatives of our country in Olympia, the World Championships, Asian Championships and international competitions, the prestige and sporting potential of Uzbekistan in the world are growing, especially valid is the fact that in the Republican regions there are facilities of competitive sports suitable for World models, the

"Sprouts of Hope", "Harmonious generation" and the Universiade, consisting of three stages, are widely distributed among students.

In competitive activities in sports games, it is possible to record TTA (technical and tactical actions) and determine the effectiveness of the actions of the general team. These indicators are a particularly criterion for athlete movements. Therefore, their account allows to plan and organize further training, and not only to reflect and restore the process of the competition, also the actions of the athlete and the team.

It is necessary to note that, taking into account the General Laws of the formation of sports skills in the chosen sport, improving the management system of the training process based on the formation of knowledge about the structure of competition activity and readiness is considered as one of the promising directions.

Improving the system of readiness for sports. At the same time, one of the most necessary elements of the athlete training management system is complex control, which ensures the implementation of various types of control, including their implementation and is used to obtain fast, objective information. There are different approaches to determine the effectiveness of competition activities in different sports. Performance indicators that are resistant to competition in front sports are often determined by drawing up regression equations in order to orientate the next direction of exercise loads, and therefore, by developing formulas and coefficients that characterize the effectiveness of an athlete's movements in the structure of his movements. All this makes it possible to emphasize the upcoming training of athletes and discuss performances in upcoming competitions.

Judging by the fact that it is written in the scientific literature, assessing the performance of actions mastered in the structure of control over competitive activities, mastering individual, group and command actions in attack and defense, assessing the effectiveness of the implementation of those who have learned are the main tasks.

The process of competition activities of handball players. Discussion and explanation of the quantitative and qualitative indicators obtained in the process of competition activities is no less than the necessary structural sections. In handball, in the conditions of competition, various movements do not fit together very often and affect the effect of the game to varying degrees. therefore, it is necessary to take into account not only the quality of performing individual actions, but also the frequency of their repetition in the game. The inclusion of these concepts in the assessment of the technical and tactical actions of handball players allows us to assess the skills of the team (the player) in an objective round and make appropriate adjustments to the training and competition processes.

In handball, the use of scientifically based methods of studying the structure and characteristics of technical and tactical competence on the basis of analytic and synthetic approaches is one of the main directions for improving the system of the training process. From the pedagogical side, the discussion of the technical and tactical activities of the national and club teams in the largest competitions at the world and mainland level makes it possible to distinguish the properties that play a leading role from the entire complex of factors affecting the importance of the team game. Based on them, by determining quantitative properties, it is possible to create exemplary characteristics of handball players of different game specialties by type of competition-resistant employability, individual team contacts, attack or defensive lines and General team.

Quantitative and qualitative indicators of the structural sections of the game itself in the practice of Handball: dribbling, throwing a cannon at the gate in different positions and cases; helping a cannon, holding a grip; tossing the ball rails sent to the gate; various counter movements of the players of the opposing team, quantitative indicators of the player's "participation" in the technical and tactical.

The most necessary properties that determine the effectiveness and structure of the technical and tactical activities of excellent teams are as follows. In violation of the game rule:

1. The number of games for the entire championship and their effectiveness.
2. The number of shots and their effectiveness: - with an individual transition from defense to attack; - in the command transition from defense to attack.
3. The number of shots in positional attacks and their effectiveness: - from 8 to 9 meters in attacks; - from 6 meters when the attack works; - when moving from corners to the attack.
4. The number of Free attempts of 7 meters and the effectiveness of their implementation.

In defense:

1. number of violations of the rules of the game: - reminders; - removal for 2 minutes ; - removal before completion of the game ; - setting a 7-meter cliff top for a rough game in defense.
2. the number of strokes thrown at the gate. The identified properties determine the effectiveness and structure of technical and tactical measures in attack and defense by hand cannon.

The modern system of training high school athletes assumes a greater development of objective instrumental methods and introduction into the training process, which gives an opportunity to assess the size of training loads and the degree of their impact on the human body. In many sports, devices and systems that determine and analyze information describing various parameters of an athlete's exercise activity are increasingly used.

Judging by the opinion of the leading experts in the field of sports, an objective system of pedagogical control of the competition activity is necessary to optimize the management of the process of improving Sports [2, 3].

In recent times, there has been a growing passion in the use of various forms of recording the actions of players in sports games, offering an assessment of their level of technical and tactical readiness [4, 5].

Among scientists and practitioners, the idea has emerged that the process of improving technical and tactical skills (TTH) can be significantly accelerated if it is increased to reality under stable monitoring conditions in the case when it uses the established quantitative and qualitative criteria for the technical and tactical readiness of athletes (TTH). It decided that it would be necessary to take into account their role in the Game [6].

Leading handball expert N. P. Klusov (1990) disagrees with the above authors ' opinion. In his opinion, the role of sports wife or team sports in the tournament table does not reflect the level of talent of athletes due to the lack of objective indicators in their quantitative indicators.

However, a number of leading sports trainers [7] believe that using special characters will lead to a significant departure from the data obtained from a common system of displaying game activity on special blanks (or ordinary paper pages), or to an excessive simplification of the recorded material. These consider that the limit of the specified parameters (technical or tactical action) of one or another component of the game will lead to a slight split. That is why

it is not for nothing that these specialists suggest that athletes collect information about the activities of the game using a specially developed code that allows you to record exhaustive information about all the parameters of technical and tactical actions on tape.

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